

An Enhanced Deep Learning Based Intrusion Detection System for IoT Networks

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Abstract - In recent years, IoT has grown rapidly connecting many different types of devices across various fields like healthcare, smart cities, industrial automation and transportation systems. IoT systems improve efficiency and automation, but they also create security challenges due to high network traffic, different devices and limited resources. These limitations make IoT networks highly vulnerable to cyber-attacks like malware, botnet and denial-of-service attacks. The existing methods are not capable enough to detect attacks that are new or changing and they also tend to generate high false alarms. To address these challenges, this work presents an enhanced intrusion detection system specifically designed for IoT networks that is built on deep learning techniques. In the proposed system, PSO is used to choose important data, while a hybrid CNN–LSTM model examines both spatial and time based patterns present in the network traffic. In addition, the system also triggers instant SMS alerts in real time, which helps to take quick response and prevention. To evaluate the proposed system, an IoT network dataset containing both regular and harmful traffic data. The experimental outcomes prove that the system can accurately detect accuracy, reduce false positive rates and maintain stable performance under real-world IoT conditions, which highlights the strength and dependability of the proposed framework.

Keywords - IoT Security, Intrusion Detection System, Deep Learning, Network Traffic Analysis, Cyber Attack Detection, CNN, LSTM

I. INTRODUCTION

The Internet of Things is transforming advanced computing by connecting devices to the internet for continuous data sharing and smart decision-making [1]. Over the past decades, IoT technologies have been used in domains like Medical application, Residential, industrial automation and smart cities.

These applications enable continuous data exchange, better monitoring and automated operations leading to improved efficiency and smarter decision making [1], [5]. The fast growth of IoT deployments has heightened the vulnerability of networked systems. IoT systems generate large amounts of network traffic, making them vulnerable to different cyber attacks such as malicious software, illegal access, compromised network activities and service disruption attacks [6], [8]. Most IoT devices possess limited processing power and memory resources, which is difficult to use access control methods used in traditional networks. This situation makes IoT systems are exposed to advanced and evolving threats [9].

IDS models are essential for maintaining the secure IoT network operations, as they continuously monitor traffic patterns and identify harmful activities based on unusual behaviour [5], [11]. Conventional IDS approaches mainly depend on predefined patterns and signature oriented techniques, which can identify only previously known threats. These techniques usually struggle to recognize emerging or unfamiliar actions and may produce excessive false positive alarms, especially in large and diverse IoT environments [6], [7].

To overcome these limitations, recent research studies employ intelligent computational approaches for threat identification in IoT ecosystems [7], [12], [19]. Advanced neural architecture can autonomously derive meaningful patterns from unprocessed network data and learn complex relationships without manual feature engineering. Specifically, CNN and LSTM networks effectively capture sequential and structural patterns in IoT traffic, leading to improved recognition accuracy and robustness [15] [18]. Based on these developments, this research develops an advanced intelligent threat detection system for IoT networks. The proposed system integrates swarm based optimization for optimal data attribute filtering with a hybrid CNN–LSTM architecture to achieve accurate traffic classification. In addition, an alert generation mechanism is integrated to deliver real-time intrusion notifications, enabling quick response and mitigation. The performance of this strategy is investigated using a publicly available network flow records that contains both normal and malicious scenarios [10].

II. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The proposed intrusion detection system designed to deliver accurate, reliable and real-time identification of cyber threats in Internet of Things environments. Because IoT devices are diverse in nature and generate large amounts of network traffic continuously, traditional security methods are not effective against modern attack attacks. To handle these difficulties, this study proposed an improved network protection framework that integrates data preprocessing, feature selection using Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO), deep learning based classification and an alert generation system. Figure 1 illustrates the overall workflow of the designed architecture.

A. System Architecture Overview

Fig 1. Overall architecture

The proposed system follows a layered architecture to provide efficient detection and response against malicious activities. Initially, the IoT network traffic is collected from a standard dataset. This data undergoes preprocessing to remove noise and normalize feature scaling. After that, PSO selects the most important features that help to improve attack detection. To optimize the feature set, it is then fed into a hybrid deep learning classifier that combines Convolutional Neural Networks and Long Short-Term Memory networks. Finally, an alert generation module sends SMS alert notification to administrators and also displays the detected suspicious or malicious traffic on the dashboard. This architecture improves detection accuracy, reduces computational complexity and enables for timely security responses in IoT networks.

B. Data Collection

Each record contains multiple traffic-related attributes. The dataset used in this research contains labelled IoT communication data with both legitimate and anomalous behavior. The data represents different IoT communication patterns and various attack behaviours such as botnet activity, denial-of-service packet statistics, protocol details, flow duration and source-destination details. The variety of traffic patterns in

the dataset help the proposed system perform effectively under real-world IoT network conditions.

C. Data Preprocessing

IoT communication data often includes incomplete values, noise and redundant features that can reduce learning performance. Therefore, pre-processing is an crucial step in the proposed methodology.

Data Cleaning

Missing and inconsistent values in the dataset are handled using appropriate imputation techniques. Duplicate and unnecessary records are removed to avoid biased learning and improve model reliability.

Data Normalization

To ensure equal contribution of all features during training, normalization method is used to adjust the feature parameters within a specific range. Here, the original feature values are adjusted based on their minimum and maximum values in the dataset. This normalization process helps improve classification performance and helps the model learn more quickly.

D. Feature Extraction

Feature engineering plays a significant role in intrusion detection framework. It converts raw or semi-processed network traffic information into an organized representation that can be effectively utilized by machine learning and deep learning models. In the present study, feature extraction is performed using flow-based and statistical attributes from the IoT network traffic dataset. Every communication flow is characterized using a multiple attributes that describe packet-level and session-level behaviour. These features include statistical measures like packet count, flow duration, average packet length, inter-arrival time, protocol type, originating, target ports details and flag-based attributes. These features capture both normal communication behaviours and malicious activities within IoT networks.

A network traffic instance is represented as a collection of extracted traffic features, where each feature corresponds to a specific network flow attribute. These features provide valuable information that helps learning models to differentiate between benign and malicious activities. Since the dataset already contains pre-extracted features, this work focuses on optimizing the feature space instead of creating new features. The extracted feature set is then passed to the feature selection stage, where optimization techniques are used to determine the most relevant features for intrusion detection.

E. PSO-Based Feature Selection

The selection of features improves intrusion detection accuracy and reduces computational complexity. In this study, Particle

Swarm Optimization is applied to select the most informative attributes from the pre-processed dataset.

Particle Representation

In the PSO based feature selection process, every particle denotes a possible combination of selected feature binary form. Each element of the particle corresponds to an specific feature from the dataset. A binary value of 1 signifies that the feature is chosen, whereas 0 indicates that the feature is not included in the selected subset.

Velocity and Position Update

The movement of particles is governed by standard Particle Swarm Optimization updating rules. Particle velocity is influenced by three factors: the previous movement, the particle's own optimal solution and the globally best solution identified by the swarm. The particle position is subsequently modified according to the updated velocity values. An inertia factor is applied to balance exploration and exploitation throughout the search process. In addition, acceleration parameters regulate the influence of both local and global learning components. Random coefficients are incorporated to enhance diversity in the search space and reduce the possibility of convergence to local optima.

Fitness Evaluation

Each particle is assessed through a fitness function that optimizes both classification performance and the minimization of selected features. The evaluation process aims to select the most informative features while minimizing the total number of selected features. This optimization process produce a compact and highly relevant feature set, which improves classification efficiency and detection accuracy

F. Deep Learning-Based Classification

Traffic analysis in IoT environments is carried out through a combined deep learning framework incorporating CNN and LSTM networks to strengthen intrusion identification capability.

CNN-Based Feature Learning

The CNN component extracts spatial features from the optimized dataset to support effective feature learning. It identifies important local characteristics and structural dependencies present in the communication patterns, helping the model recognize suspicious activities more effectively.

LSTM-Based Temporal Learning

The LSTM module is used to learn temporal and sequential patterns present in IoT network traffic. It analyzes traffic behavior over time and returns important contextual information through its memory capability. This helps the system detect complex attack behaviors and long-term malicious patterns more accurately.

G. Alert Generation Mechanism

An alert generation module is integrated into the system to provide real-time SMS notifications whenever malicious traffic is detected. If the classification result exceeds a predefined threat threshold, an alert is generated and recorded for further analysis. This mechanism enables quick response and enhances the real world applicability of the proposed IoT intrusion detection framework. In addition, a dashboard can be integrated to display the type of detected attack along with possible mitigation methods, helping administrators monitor and handle security threats more effectively.

H. Performance Evaluation Metrics

Metrics	Value	Description
Accuracy	0.98	Represents the overall correctness of the model in classifying network traffic
Precision	0.99	Indicates the proportion of correctly predicted intrusion instances.
Recall	0.98	Measures the ability of the model to identify actual intrusion activities.
F1-score	1.00	Provides a balanced evaluation of precision and recall performance.
Macro Average F1-Score	0.99	Shows the average classification performance across all classes.
Weighted Average F1-score	0.98	Reflects overall performance by considering class distribution.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This part describes the experimental findings of the PSO assisted deep learning driven intrusion detection framework for IoT environments. Various visualizations and evaluation metrics are utilized to examine network data behaviour, feature relationships, model learning performance and attack detection capability. Each figure is discussed in detail to demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed method.

Fig 2. Traffic class distribution

Fig 2 shows the arrangement of normal and intrusion data flow in the IoT network records. It can be seen that intrusion traffic samples are higher than normal traffic samples. This reflects real-world IoT environments, where attacks like botnets and automated threats produce a large amount of unusual network traffic. The imbalance in the dataset emphasizes the importance of using strong learning models that can effectively detect intrusions without favouring the majority groups.

Fig 3. Protocol-wise traffic distribution

Fig 3 shows how normal and intrusion traffic are distributed across different network protocols in the IoT dataset. The results indicate that some protocols are more commonly associated with malicious activities than others. A large portion of intrusion traffic is concentrated in specific protocol categories, showing that attackers often exploit weaknesses present in certain communication protocols used in IoT networks. This analysis helps in understanding which protocols are more vulnerable to attacks and provides useful insights into network behaviour. It also demonstrates that protocol related features carry important information for identifying malicious activities. Therefore, these

features are selected to increase the efficiency and detection capability of the intrusion detection system.

Fig 4. Packet length comparison

Fig 4 comparison of total forward packet size for normal and intrusion related network activity. The findings indicate that intrusion related network activity exhibits greater variation and larger packet lengths than normal activity. This pattern reflects abnormal communication behavior often linked with attack activities such as flooding and unauthorized data transfer. The difference between normal and malicious traffic demonstrates that packet-level statistical features are highly useful for distinguishing intrusion activities from regular network behavior. Therefore, these features significantly contribute to enhancing the performance of the intrusion detection system.

Fig 5. Feature correlation heatmap

Fig 5 illustrates the correlation heatmap of extracted network traffic features. A strong relationship can be observed among features related to packet length, transmission time and transmission interval. Highly correlated features may create redundancy and increase computational complexity during model training. This analysis supports the use of PSO for selecting most relevant and non-redundant features. The proposed approach improves model efficiency and detection accuracy.

Fig 6. Training and validation accuracy

Fig 7. Training and validation loss

Fig 6 and Fig 7 illustrate the performance of CNN-LSTM model during the learning phase by presenting training and validation accuracy along with loss values. The accuracy curves show consistent improvement and remain closely matched throughout the training stages, showing effective learning with minimal overfitting. In addition, the training and validation loss gradually decrease over successive epochs, indicating that the model converges efficiently during learning. Minor fluctuations in validation loss are expected due to the changing characteristics of IoT communication data. Overall, the findings verify the reliability, stability and high detection capability of the intrusion detection framework.

Classification Report:				
	precision	recall	f1-score	support
0	1.00	0.94	0.97	8015
1	1.00	1.00	1.00	117142
accuracy			1.00	125157
macro avg	1.00	0.97	0.98	125157
weighted avg	1.00	1.00	1.00	125157

Fig 8. Classification report

The classification results indicate the strong efficiency of the developed intrusion detection framework. Both normal and intrusion classes obtain strong precision, recall and F1 score values, indicating dependable and accurate classification performance. Notably, the intrusion category attains a very high recall value, indicating that the model can identify nearly all malicious activities with minimal missed attacks. The high

precision values also indicate a minimal false alarm rate, enhancing the reliability of the introduced system. Overall, the classification results confirm that the proposed CNN-LSTM model with PSO based feature selection is highly effective in identifying malicious network traffic while maintaining strong overall detection accuracy.

Fig 9. Confusion Matrix

The confusion matrix illustrates the classification capability of the proposed framework. The model effectively distinguishes normal and harmful network activity with minimal misclassification. Strong true positive and true negative rates demonstrate that the system can effectively identify harmful activities while reducing false alerts. This capability is important for maintaining reliable and secure IoT network environments.

Fig 10. ROC curve

In the developed system, the true positive rate remains strong while the false negative rate stays minimal, allowing the ROC curve to approach the top-left region, which reflects effective classification performance. The strong accuracy value further confirms that the developed intrusion detection framework can efficiently differentiate normal and harmful network activity.

Fig 11. Intrusion detection timeline

Fig 11 shows the intrusion detection timeline generated using a sliding window approach. Periodic spikes in the graph represent the occurrence of attack activities within the IoT network traffic. This time-based analysis highlights the ability of the proposed model to continuously observe network activity and detect intrusions in real time environments. The results indicate that the system can successfully detect sudden changes and unusual traffic patterns associated with malicious activities. This real-time monitoring capability improves the dependability and adaptability of the developed intrusion detection framework in dynamic IoT environments.

Fig 12. Average intrusion trend

The average intrusion trend shows the frequency of detected attacks over successive time windows. The consistent detection pattern indicates that the proposed system maintains stable reliable performance even under varying traffic conditions. This stability indicates that the model can efficiently observe IoT network activity over time and precisely identify malicious activities. Therefore, the developed system is effective for use in real-world IoT network deployment.

Fig 13. Severity level distribution

Fig 13 shows the distribution of detected intrusions based on different severity levels. The findings show that the developed system can efficiently categorize intrusions into low, medium and high risk levels. This capability supports prioritized alert generation and allows administrations to respond more faster to critical security threats.

The dashboard visualization integrates traffic statistics, intrusion trends, severity levels and alert information into a single interface. This provides network administrators with a clear and comprehensive overview of IoT security status, improving situational awareness and decision-making efficiency.

Fig 14. Alert Generation and SMS Notification

An alert generation mechanism is integrated into the proposed system to provide immediate notifications whenever an intrusion is detected. Along with system alerts, SMS notifications are also sent to the administrator to ensure that critical security information is delivered without delay even if the system is not actively monitored. This mechanism improves response time, enables faster threat mitigation and minimizes the impact of possible cyber threats in IoT environments.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper presents a Particle Swarm Optimization assisted deep learning method to improve intrusion detection in Internet of Things networks. The developed framework combines data preprocessing, feature extraction, PSO driven feature selection and a hybrid CNN-LSTM model to accurately identify harmful activities in IoT network communication. By optimizing the feature set, the framework reduces redundant information and increases computational complexity while improving the overall detection performance and classification accuracy..

Experimental evaluation performed on the IoT network flow dataset demonstrates that the developed PSO enhanced deep learning intrusion detection framework achieves strong accuracy, precision, recall and F1 score values in identifying harmful activities. The results confirm that the model can effectively distinguish between normal and attack traffic with very low false alarm rates, thereby improving the reliability of intrusion detection in IoT environments. The optimized feature selection process reduces redundant and irrelevant information, which decreases computational complexity while improving classification efficiency and overall detection performance.

Furthermore, the integration of a real time alert generation mechanism enhances the practical usability of the system. Whenever abnormal or harmful activity is identified, the system produces instant alerts and delivers SMS notifications to administrators, enabling rapid response and threat mitigation. The dashboard visualization further improves monitoring capability by presenting intrusion trends, traffic statistics, severity levels and alert information through a single interface. Overall, the proposed PSO based deep learning intrusion detection framework offers an effective, reliable and scalable approach for securing IoT networks against continuously evolving cyber threats.

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